

Bridging the Digital Divide: The XGain Knowledge Facilitation Tool for Rural Connectivity

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Abstract—This paper presents the development and application of the XGain Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT), designed to address the digital divide in rural areas by enhancing knowledge about use and deployment of digital infrastructure and supporting socio-environmental and techno-economic sustainability. The XGain project focuses on empowering rural stakeholders by providing them with a robust digital tool that facilitates informed decision-making, leveraging state-of-the-art telecommunication technologies. The KFT integrates socio-environmental and techno-economic assessments, as well as business model proposals, offering a comprehensive solution to the unique challenges faced by rural communities. The project highlights the importance of tailored digital solutions to foster resilience, competitiveness, and inclusivity in rural areas, ensuring they are not left behind in the global digital transformation.

Index Terms—Digitalization of Rural Areas, Knowledge Facilitation Tool, Socio-environmental Assessment, Techno-Economic Assessment,

I. INTRODUCTION

Emerging trends in telecommunication technologies, such as telecommuting and online commerce, alongside global efforts to enhance digital infrastructure in sectors like healthcare, education, transportation, and agriculture, are further exposing the digital access disparities between regions, particularly undermining the resilience and prosperity of rural communities. The digital access and high-speed connectivity gap between urban and rural areas remains significant [1]. Rural communities, key players in managing and leveraging natural resources, face not only technological deficiencies but also unequal opportunities and socio-environmental sustainability challenges. Addressing accessibility and connectivity is crucial to counter the erosion of socio-territorial cohesion, especially as rural and coastal populations are highly vulnerable to the digital divide. Strengthening community resilience, competitiveness, and capacity is vital for ensuring a just and balanced transition during

upcoming technological shifts. However, empowering rural communities with better access to services, opportunities, and innovation ecosystems—while ensuring inclusivity—remains a complex task due to the diverse challenges and requirements across different locations.

The XGain project [2] plays an important role in promoting sustainable development across rural, coastal, and urban areas. The XGain consortium is formed by 17 partners from 11 countries, featuring technological and social research organizations, SMEs, industrial partners and a governmental organization. XGain aims to achieve its goals by facilitating direct engagement with rural stakeholders to co-create solutions, including farmers, their associations, local or regional authorities, and policymakers. The project's centerpiece is the Knowledge Facilitation Tool (KFT), which helps devise business models and supports informed decision-making on technology ecosystems, encompassing connectivity and edge computing solutions for rural services. The KFT evaluates the techno-economic and socio-environmental impacts of ICT infrastructures and digital services across various sectors. Unlike typical planning tools, the KFT is designed for non-expert users, offering an intuitive, user-friendly dashboard and simplifying complex technical requirements. XGain addresses challenges such as enhancing systemic resilience, improving energy efficiency, mitigating climate change, and bridging the digital divide across citizens, agricultural sectors, and regions. To assess the KFT's benefits, six rural pilots across Europe are evaluating the practical implications of ICT usage in rural environments.

This paper outlines the scope of the KFT and the challenges it addresses, detailing the methodologies used for its design and implementation, as well as initial outcomes. In Section II, we introduce the KFT and its key features as a central element of the project. Section III provides a detailed overview of the design and implementation process. The testing and

validation procedures, along with the initial outcomes from the first two years of the project, are presented in Section IV. Finally, Section V concludes the paper and outlines the next steps for the XGain project.

II. XGAIN KNOWLEDGE FACILITATION TOOL

The core objective of the XGain project is the development of the web-based KFT focused on user input and personalized solution recommendations. It is part of XGain’s initiative to guide rural stakeholders in deploying ICT infrastructures for their services. Designed for non-expert users, the KFT features a user-friendly dashboard that supports multi-actor engagement and provides accessible outputs for non-technical stakeholders. The dashboard allows users to select specific sectors or multi-sector assessments, input location-specific needs, and specify the assessment level (regional, community, or farm). Based on this input, the KFT suggests connectivity and edge processing solutions tailored to the requirements of digitalized services, while also offering assessments for various impact categories and customized business plans.

To suggest technology mixes, the project undertook a comprehensive stocktaking of connectivity and edge processing enablers. The KFT evaluates both wired and wireless solutions based on deployment points and their interconnections within a physical area. Additionally, the project develops algorithmic solutions for service optimization, addressing service placement and system dimensioning. The KFT incorporates both techno-economic and socio-environmental assessment models to ensure that the proposed technology solutions are not only feasible but also sustainable and beneficial to rural communities. These models evaluate factors such as the financial viability of connectivity and edge processing solutions, their energy consumption, and their broader socio-environmental impacts, including effects on community well-being and biodiversity. By integrating these assessments, the KFT provides users with a holistic understanding of how different technology mixes will perform across economic, environmental, and social dimensions. Business model innovation is central to promoting the adoption of next-generation, last-mile, and edge solutions in rural and remote areas. This involves a thorough analysis of business model feasibility and a techno-economic and socio-environmental impact assessment. The project aims to recommend innovative, viable solutions to improve access to services, opportunities, and innovation ecosystems. In the next section, we outline the methodologies used in designing the KFT and the outcomes of its implementation.

III. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF THE KFT

The design process of the KFT, as described in the previous section, faced several cross-disciplinary challenges. The tool not only had to deliver technically complex features, such as suggesting multipart technology mixes and ICT infrastructures for rural services, but also assess various impact factors and propose suitable business models across multiple sectors. Furthermore, it needed to remain accessible and user-friendly, ensuring that even users with minimal ICT knowledge could

navigate it effectively. In this section, we present the key methodologies applied in designing the KFT and discuss how the project engaged rural stakeholders to capture their needs and translate them into system requirements. We also provide details on the implementation of some of the key models and tools within the KFT.

A. The XGain Knowledge Alliance: Co-Creation with rural stakeholders

Co-creation plays a crucial role in legitimizing innovation processes and fostering shared ownership or accountability among multiple stakeholders [3]. The European Commission uses the concept of co-creation in their definition of public engagement in responsible research and innovation, which they define as “*co-creating the future with citizens and civil society organisations, and bringing on board the widest possible diversity of actors that would not normally interact with each other, on matters of science and technology*” (European Commission, 2016). This co-creation plays a crucial role in the XGain project activities, and for shaping the KFT. The applied approach ensures the participation of diverse stakeholders – such as from policymaking – and fosters the empowerment of local communities contributing to and benefitting from knowledges production and innovations. Furthermore, it encompasses governance aspects aligned with policies for a smoother implementation and the subsequent exploitation of results. All efforts aimed to increase the social acceptance of the project activities and outcomes. As such, the 6 use case sites of the project have identified relevant stakeholders, seeking a transition from a Triple Helix model, involving public sector, academia, and private sector, to a Quadruple Helix model that includes civil society. Civil society is represented by NGOs, and the process facilitates engagement across various stakeholder groups, incorporating community perspectives. The XGain approach also extends the social value chain beyond organizational activities, considering broader impacts on communities. Pop-up co-creation labs, implemented as compact workshops in five use case regions, generated concrete results by fostering collaboration across local, regional, and trans-regional levels in sustainability transitions at the technology-society-environment nexus. These labs facilitated equal contributions of target, system, and transformational knowledge, supporting the socially accepted change envisioned by XGain solutions and services.

This ecosystem of stakeholders created in the first 2 years of the project was framed as the “XGain Knowledge Alliance”. The project considers it an alliance, since the co-creation and interactions with stakeholders is not only of use for the project, but also for the stakeholders as the project creates value by exposing its outcomes and eventually provides the KFT to them. Beyond the co-creation process, surveys and interactive webinars allowed to gather specific feedback on how the KFT should be designed, visually and in terms of features. All the user’s needs and suggestions were captured and used to better define the requirements of the KFT. The methodology used to determine these requirements is detailed below.

B. KFT Architecture Design

The architecture definition process for the KFT was divided into three phases. In Phase 1, the tool's nature, scope, and purpose were defined, along with gathering requirements. Phase 2 focused on identifying the high-level architecture, mapping functionalities, and specifying technical details. Finally, Phase 3 involved creating an implementation and deployment plan for the finalized architecture.

This subsection presents the outcomes of phases 1 and 2, detailing how the KFT's requirements were gathered and translated into its software architecture. Given the KFT aims to help rural actors identify technological solutions for introducing or upgrading digital services, understanding their needs and transforming them into tool functionalities is critical. Although the XGain project's grant agreement outlines a specific functional scope, a more detailed definition of the KFT and its features emerged through technical project tasks and direct engagement with rural stakeholders to gather requirements.

Due to the limited technical knowledge of rural stakeholders regarding software architectures and advanced digital technologies, direct requirements could not be gathered. Instead, stakeholders provided user stories, which identified an actor (e.g., the KFT user), their desired actions, and the intended outcome. A total of 151 user stories were collected, focusing on high-level functional details, rural services for digitalization, dashboard design, and more. These user stories were then translated into 45 Functional and Non-Functional Requirements (FRs and NFRs), covering all key aspects for KFT implementation. Further consolidation categorized these requirements and identified dependencies between them. Finally, the MoSCoW method [4] was applied to prioritize which FRs and NFRs would be implemented in the KFT and which were out of scope.

At this stage, the second phase of the architecture design methodology was applied to define the key architecture building blocks and their interaction patterns, laying the foundation for the KFT software implementation. To support this design phase, use cases and workflow diagrams were created to illustrate the interaction between users and the KFT dashboard, as well as the interactions between underlying software components, such as data sets, formats, and interfaces. The complete breakdown of the final KFT architecture (including detailed requirements, user stories, workflows and use cases) and the initial implementation are detailed in the project's deliverables D2.4 and D4.7 [5], respectively.

The architecture consists of six main backend models (M1-M6), alongside the front-end dashboard. A brief overview of these building blocks is as follows: The dashboard provides several views for users to input information and receive assessments. At a session's start, users provide basic details such as stakeholder type, sectors, services, and the country for which the assessment is to be conducted. The KFT also considers environmental factors relevant to the deployment location, such as typical weather conditions and topographical features, in addition to the types of devices to be deployed.

Fig. 1: *Technology Mix Finder & Dimensioning Solver* architecture

Based on the provided information, the *Technology Mix Finder* (M1) and *Dimensioning Solver* (M2) models identify infrastructure technology mixes that meet user-defined requirements for radio communication and computing devices, considering both quantity and quality. The *Techno-Economic Assessment* model (M3) evaluates these mixes with respect to techno-economic factors such as Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) and Operating expense (OPEX). The *Socio-Environmental Assessment* model (M4) uses user input, such as country and targeted sectors or services, to provide a socio-environmental evaluation of the proposed solutions. The user determines which assessment categories are most relevant via the dashboard, and these preferences are processed by the *Impact Weights Assessment* module (M5). This module ranks the best solutions from M1&M2 based on user priorities and requests detailed assessment results from the other models for the top-ranking options. Finally, the *Business Model Proposer* (M6) generates a business model canvas based on the selected sectors and services, which is displayed on the dashboard as part of the output. The following subsections provide further details on how these assessment models function.

C. Design of Functional and Assessment models

At the forefront of the KFT is the dashboard, which serves as the primary interface between the user and the models. It facilitates the generation of technology mix proposals, provides techno-economic and socio-environmental assessments, and suggests suitable business models. User-friendliness, even for non-technical users, has been a key design focus since the project's beginning. Extracting essential information from users in an understandable way, without requiring knowledge of technical details, was crucial. For the KFT to produce precise outputs, it still requires details about radio communications (e.g., transmission speeds) and computation needs (e.g., RAM and CPU) of the services to be deployed. However, co-creation sessions with rural stakeholders showed that such terms are often unfamiliar or unclear. To enhance accessibility, the KFT uses conversational, user-friendly language, avoiding technical jargon. For example, instead of asking for performance metrics, the KFT frames questions around practical user experiences. Iconography, tooltips, and help sections further improve clarity, minimizing the technical knowledge required.

This approach minimizes the level of technical knowledge required by users as much as possible. Once the user has provided all inputs, the technology mix finder and dimensioning solver models (M1&M2) evaluate which ICT infrastructure setups are suited to satisfy the technical requirements. Based on the users' inputs and the available data sets of communication technologies and processing devices collected by XGain's partners, the models identify suitable technology mixes. These solutions include an appropriate filtering of possible communication networks and the calculation of the number of the necessary components to meet demand, as well as the selection of the type, number and location of processing devices in the compute-continuum (CC) to host any processing tasks. The 'Processing Modelling' block (see top of Fig.1) executes a binary integer non-linear programming (BINLP) optimization problem, taking into account the user's service latency constraints and minimizing system power consumption, following the hierarchical tree-based concept presented in [6]. The design of optimization frameworks for appropriate processing task allocations in CC is of utmost importance, with extensive related literature, such as [7]. While most of the works predetermine the type and number of available processing devices, this is part of the problem solved by our designed mechanism. Moreover, considering the user-friendliness of the KFT tool and the time-consuming nature of the optimization processes, special attention has been given to deliver quick and valid results, ensuring the optimization problem is designed and structured efficiently.

For the layout of infrastructure suggestions, a hierarchical 4-node deployment model (shown below the 'Output' block in Fig.1) has been designed to accommodate a wide range of user scenarios. This model allows computation nodes executing processing tasks of a digitalized service to be collocated in four tiers: i) in the extreme edge, i.e., with the end devices (like drones), ii) at the far edge, i.e., with the radio communication nodes, e.g., a 5G base station, iii) at the near edge, i.e., a central point in the area where the services are deployed, and iv) in the cloud, i.e., physically separated from where the services are deployed. The first three tiers fall under 'private' infrastructure, while the 'cloud' node belongs to the 'public' infrastructure, utilizing resources from cloud providers like AWS. To connect these tiers, the KFT assumes a series of communication hops (*Access*, *Local* and *Internet*) where specific wired, or wireless communication technologies that satisfy the communication requirements are suggested.

The outcome of the technology mix finding and dimensioning process includes the specification of both the number and type of networks in the communication hops, as well as the processing devices across the tiers. To select and allocate these processing devices to the CC, information about the inference latency and processing loads of user's services across various processing devices has been collected by XGain's consortium. The KFT evaluates 50 state-of-the-art technologies, including 30 communication and 24 computing technologies, for which a detailed stocktaking was conducted based on either scientific literature, market vendors, and the consortium's expertise.

Specifically, both wired networks (e.g., fiber) and wireless networks (e.g., cellular, non-cellular, Internet of Things (IoT), and satellite) are considered. Additionally, the technology mix finder and dimensioning solver models include a broad range of processing devices with varying capacities. These range from lightweight devices like Raspberry Pis and NVIDIA single-board computers to more powerful NUCs and rack-mounted servers, both with and without GPUs, to address the specific demands of the user's services.

The output of models M1&M2 are fed into model M3, the techno-economic model, which is used to assess the suggested technology mixes. The methodology used in M3, adopted from previous studies [8], has been enhanced to include edge computing solutions. The core part of the techno-economic model is in a database (DB), which includes data related to network components as well as to processing and end-users devices. This DB is regularly updated with data collected from the largest European telecommunication companies and vendors, as well as from benchmarks from the telecom market [8], [9]. The study period, a crucial aspect of the techno-economic model, is tailored to the specific case under investigation. For network deployments, where it takes time for a network or service to achieve market maturity and recoup investments, an eight to ten-year period is considered reasonable, with a ten-year period assumed in the KFT. A price evolution for all network components is determined using the extended learning curve model [10] and component replacement is factored in based on lifecycle estimates. Capital Expenditure (CAPEX) is determined by multiplying the number of required components by their annual prices.

Operational, Administration, and Maintenance (OA&M) expenditures are also considered. Energy costs are evaluated based on the power consumption of components and average kWh prices, accounting also for idle periods [11]. Maintenance costs are also estimated consisting of two parts: (i) the cost of repair, calculated as a fixed percentage of the total investments in network elements, and; (ii) the cost of repair work, that has been calculated based on the Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF) and the Mean Time To Repair (MTTR). In case some parts of existing networks (public networks) are used, connectivity fees are estimated and included in OPEX. Model M3 outputs the total CAPEX and OPEX, along with time series data for CAPEX components, OPEX categories, and other metrics to support user decision-making.

Model M4 is essential in providing a comprehensive socio-environmental assessment of the technology options suggested by M1&M2. On the environmental side, it evaluates the energy consumption of network and processing devices, calculating their carbon footprint. The country information provided by the user helps ensure that the carbon footprint calculations are region-specific by selecting the appropriate emission factor for the local electricity grid. Additionally, the model can highlight potential resource savings, such as water and fertilizer, for services like agriculture. These environmental factors and the carbon footprint are analyzed for their impact on biodiversity using data from LC-IMPACT [12], giving users insight of how

their technology choices may affect local ecosystems.

The environmental ranking of technology options is based on their carbon footprint, with solutions scored from 1 (lowest footprint) to 0.1 (highest footprint). These scores, along with other indicators such as energy use, impact on human health, and effects on biodiversity, complete the environmental assessment and form part of the outputs shown to the user.

On the social side, M4 uses a self-assessment process to gather users' perspectives on how adopting new technologies might affect social factors such as worker well-being, local communities, and broader societal issues. This is combined with a top-down selection of key social impact areas, ensuring that important aspects like employment conditions, community engagement, and access to resources are fully considered. For instance, in the agricultural sector, users may be prompted to reflect on issues such as labour conditions or the availability of essential resources. User responses are scored as follows: Highly positive (+2), Slightly positive (+1), No effect (0), Slightly negative (-1), and Highly negative (-2). These social impact scores represent the user's expectations of how the technology will influence these social dimensions. Once the self-assessment is complete, the social scores are combined with the environmental scores to provide an overall ranking of the technology solutions. The aim of this process is to support users in making informed decisions that consider not only the technical and environmental aspects but also the social impact of their technology choices.

Models M1-M4 generate scores for technology mixes across various categories, including technological, economic, environmental, and social factors. These scores consider aspects such as pricing, future readiness, and energy consumption. Model M5, the impact weights assessment model, allows users to assign weights to each category based on their preferences. The combination of these weights and scores produces an overall score for each technology mix, enabling the sorting and presentation of options to the user. Once a technology mix is selected, detailed assessment results are shown in a dedicated output overview.

In addition to the technology mix suggestions and corresponding assessments, the Business Model analysis (M6) delivers innovative business models that identify key success factors for the effective implementation of the aforementioned novel services. These models support decision-making processes aimed at enhancing digital connectivity in rural communities. The analysis provides tailored business models for three types of actors: (i) End users (e.g., farmers, SMEs), (ii) Local or regional Internet Service Providers (ISPs) and Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), and (iii) Public Authorities, based on their connectivity needs and ambitions across various sectors (Figure 2).

After a benchmarking on a plethora of business model tools, the *Business Model Canvas* was chosen as the most suitable for addressing the needs of XGain's use cases and KFT users [14]. Its wide acceptance, versatility, and ability to foster stakeholder collaboration makes it ideal for tackling the unique challenges of digital connectivity in rural areas

AGRICULTURE Precision Agriculture Drones Operation Livestock Health Farm Management	AQUACULTURE Remote Farming Water quality monitoring Broadband Connectivity	EDUCATION Distance Learning High Data Rate Services Broadband Connectivity	EHEALTH Health Monitoring Broadband Connectivity	ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING Water quality monitoring Land Use/ Land Cover Broadband Connectivity
Remote Farming Smart Farming Broadband Connectivity	EGOVERNANCE Government eServices Land Use/ Land Cover Broadband Connectivity	FORESTRY Forest management Broadband Connectivity	TOURISM Leisure Broadband Connectivity	

Fig. 2: Sectors (8) and services (15) covered by the XGain business models

[13]. Furthermore, in conjunction with the *Public Governance Model Canvas* that emphasizes on value creation, both public and private sectors can be supported, facilitating decision-making on digital connectivity for all three types of actors.

For end users and ISPs/MNOs, the canvas helps to identify key partners, activities, and resources necessary for business success. It outlines value propositions, customer relationships, channels, segments, cost structure, and potential revenue streams. For public governance users (authorities), the canvas emphasizes how implementing novel services can benefit the community or region by focusing on public value, potential stakeholders, and partnerships or collaborations. XGain integrates techno-economic feasibility with social and environmental impacts to develop and validate business models in six use cases. These models are refined through five online co-design workshops and a feedback survey to ensure market effectiveness. XGain engaged stakeholders to gather input, which helped optimize the models. Testing and validation ensure that both the business models and the KFT platform meet functionality, performance, security, and usability requirements. Next steps include developing cross-sector business models to improve digital connectivity in underserved rural areas. A deployment guide will be created for local ISPs, MNOs, and Public Authorities, while exploring partnerships and financing strategies to ensure long-term success.

Having outlined the functions of models M1 through M6, several example indicative output views generated by the KFT are shown, providing a visual representation of how these models work together to deliver tailored recommendations and assessments to the end user (Fig. 3, detailed figures available in D4.7 [5]). Fig. 3a shows the top 3 of technology mix proposals proposed as a result of the inputs provided by a user. Fig. 3b and Fig. 3c depict the correspondent techno-economic and socio-environmental assessments, respectively. Finally, the end user business model canvas is presented in Fig. 3d.

IV. PILOTS AND KFT VALIDATION

The XGain project implements six use cases across Europe to demonstrate the benefits of digital solutions for rural sectors, validating three key components: the technological solutions of the KFT, the KFT's functionality, and the broader socio-environmental, economic, and technological impacts. The use cases span various domains, including rural community services in Spain, e-Health in Greece, precision agriculture in the UK, forestry in Lithuania, aquaculture in Croatia, and livestock management in Belgium. Each case provides a unique testing ground for the KFT, from monitoring coastal oyster farms with IoT devices to using drones for forest fire prevention.

(a) Technology mix proposal output

(b) Techno-Economic assessment output

(c) Socio-Environmental assessment output

(d) End user business model canvas

Fig. 3: Collection of indicative output views produced by the KFT for a user session

The first validation component tests the recommended technological solutions in a two-stage process: technologies undergo dry-run testing in a controlled laboratory environment to evaluate reliability, performance, and suitability. Then, end-to-end (E2E) field trials are conducted at the six use case locations, integrating connectivity and edge processing technologies to assess their effectiveness in real-world conditions to ensure the solutions meet the specific needs of each sector across varied environmental and technical contexts

The second validation area focuses on the KFT as a decision-making tool for rural stakeholders. This process tests the dashboard's ability to provide accurate, reliable, and practical solutions by integrating connectivity, edge processing technologies, and socio-economic assessments. During field trials, use case leaders input specific data into the KFT, allowing it to generate tailored technological solutions, business models, and impact assessments. Experts then compare the KFT's outputs with real-world conditions, identifying potential improvements, such as algorithm tweaks or bug fixes. Additionally, the KFT's recommendations can inform and optimize use case deployments.

From the start, rural stakeholders have been involved via workshops and webinars to help define the KFT's scope and design. The remainder of the project will involve E2E testing, with external users completing the full KFT process. Feedback will be collected with on-site/online workshops, and by granting XGain Knowledge Alliance members access to the KFT with only built-in guidance. Feedback from both methods is critical for refining usability, ensuring accessibility for non-expert users, and delivering insights across sectors and regions.

The final validation process assesses the broader impact of the technological solutions and the KFT's outputs. This involves impact assessments evaluating the technological, economic, environmental, and social effects of the implemented solutions. Use case leaders gather key performance indicators (KPIs) to measure outcomes in each domain. A critical factor in this process is social acceptance, ensuring that the solutions are not only technically feasible but also culturally and ethically appropriate for the communities they serve. This impact validation confirms that the solutions align with the project's broader sustainability goals and meet the needs of rural communities.

A. Initial Outcomes

The first integrated version of the KFT, which includes the dashboard, all models, and inter-model workflows, supports assessments at the farm level and for individual sector-service combinations. As outlined earlier, testing and validation of this version focused on dashboard stability and model integrity, leading to refinements and extended interfaces to support all planned features. Feedback from rural stakeholders and the interim project review was largely positive, with suggestions mainly aimed at improving the user interface, such as adding tooltips to guide users through dashboard views. Additionally, deployment improvements were made, with the KFT now running in a virtual machine while the models are containerized.

The first series of online use case workshops, titled “Advancing Rural Connectivity Together,” successfully employed a co-creation methodology to actively involve stakeholders in optimizing the KFT. These workshops showcased the KFT and business models, gathering valuable feedback and fostering collaborative dialogue. Participants included MNOs, ISPs, public authorities, farmers, aquaculture practitioners, elderly residents, and forest managers. The feedback focused on user experience, ease of use, and the effectiveness of the assessment modules and business models. This collaborative approach helped tailor the KFT to rural community needs, refining business models and enhancing usability and functionality.

Regarding the testing and validation of XGain’s technological solutions at the six pilot sites, operational environments have been successfully established, including the installation and configuration of hardware components. Integration of end-devices has been completed, ensuring system functionality. Use case leaders identified test scenarios based on each use case’s specific needs and impacts, and initial measurements are being taken to evaluate technological KPIs and E2E performance. Any issues are being addressed, with feedback used to fine-tune the solutions.

For the broader impact assessment of the KFT and XGain solutions—covering technological, economic, environmental, and social effects—use case leaders have successfully engaged key stakeholders for KPI evaluation. These stakeholders contributed and will continue contributing data through interviews, surveys, and questionnaires, providing valuable insights for the ongoing impact assessment across all domains.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

This paper presented the development and implementation of the XGain KFT, designed to bridge the digital divide in rural areas by improving digital infrastructure and promoting socio-environmental and techno-economic sustainability. The KFT is a key resource for rural stakeholders, equipping them with the tools and knowledge needed to make informed decisions and fully leverage emerging telecommunication technologies.

By integrating socio-environmental and techno-economic assessments, refined through co-creation activities with rural stakeholders, the tool provides a comprehensive solution to the unique challenges faced by rural communities. The XGain project demonstrates the potential of tailored digital solutions

in fostering resilience and prosperity in these regions. Furthermore, the project emphasizes the ongoing need for digital inclusion efforts to ensure rural areas are not left behind in the global digital transformation.

Future work will focus on refining the KFT by incorporating user feedback and expanding its capabilities to address a broader range of rural needs. The XGain Knowledge Alliance will be strengthened by engaging new rural agents and maintaining involvement from current members. As of this writing, co-creation workshops with local authorities in the six use case countries are underway to identify scalable policy recommendations that can help close the digital gap.

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